

George and Davina Huxley on Ithaca (Courtesy of Robert McCabe)

On Homer's Ithaca

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Dedicated to John V. Luce

INTRODUCTORY NOTE: *In the summer of 2007 Robert and Dina McCabe and their daughter Anne kindly invited my wife and me to join them in a voyage to and around Ithaca and Kefalonia. Well equipped with texts, including Homer and Strabo, and with binoculars, maps, charts and cameras, we proposed to test hypotheses purporting to show that modern Ithaca (Ἰθάκη or Θιάκη) was not the island of Odysseus since, so it had been claimed, the hero lived elsewhere — for example in Kefalonia or in Leukas (Lefkas or Lefkada). We visited many parts of Ithaca and Kefalonia, and subsequently lectures were given by me in England, Ireland and the United States with the title Ulixes redux: why the island called Ithaki today is Homer's Ithaca. The purpose of this brief essay is to assure readers that the Ithaki (Ithaca, Ἰθάκη or Θιάκη) illustrated here by Mr McCabe's fine photographs is indeed the island home of the heroic son of Laertes. (September 2012)*

Let us begin with the *Iliad*. In the Catalogue of Ships in Book II of the poem it is stated that Odysseus ruled over the Kephallenians. Then it defines the areas of his kingdom (Hom. *Il.* 2.631–637):

αὐτὰρ Ὀδυσσεὺς ἦγε Κεφαλλήνας μεγαθύμους,
οἳ ῥ' Ἰθάκην εἶχον καὶ Νήριτον εἰνοσίφυλλον
καὶ Κροκύλει' ἐνέμοντο καὶ Αἰγίλιπα τρηχεῖαν,
οἳ τε Ζάκυνθον ἔχον ἠδ' οἳ Σάμον ἀμφενέμοντο,
οἳ τ' ἠπειρον ἔχον ἠδ' ἀντιπέραι' ἐνέμοντο:
τῶν μὲν Ὀδυσσεὺς ἦρχε Διὶ μῆτιν ἀτάλαντος:
τῶ δ' ἅμα νῆες ἔποντο δυώδεκα μιλτοπάρηοι.

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But Odysseus led the high-hearted men of Kephallenia,
those who held Ithaca and leaf-trembling Neriton,
those who dwelt about Krokyleia and rugged Aigilips,¹
those who held Zakynthos and those who dwelt about Samos,
those who held the mainland and the places next to the crossing.
All these men were led by Odysseus, like Zeus in counsel.
Following with him were twelve ships with bows red painted.

Places mentioned in his kingdom are (see Map 1, page 28):

1. The town or polis of Ithaca on the island of that name.
2. Neritos, the district dominated by the mountain of that name in Ithaca.
3. Krokyleia and Aigilips; these places are not identified with certainty but, like Neritos, they may well be districts of Ithaca.
4. Zacynthos, today the island of Zakynthos or Zante.
5. Samos, or Samē, an ancient name of Kefalonia where the toponym survives in the modern town of Sami.
6. The mainland (ἡπειρος) and the lands over against the mainland (ἀντιπέραια). It should be noted that the nearest mainland to Ithaca is Acarnania.

Laertes and his son Odysseus belonged to a race, or tribe, called Kephallenians, but Homer referred to the island now called Kefalonia as Samos, or Samē. Only centuries after the time of Laertes, Odysseus and Homer, the name of the Kephallenian race attached itself to the island of Samos–Samē.

The islands and places ascribed to the kingdom of Odysseus in the Catalogue of Ships fit well a statement the hero himself made to the Phaeacian king, Alkinoos (*Hom. Od.* 9.21–24):

ναιετάα δ' Ἰθάκην ἐυδείελον: ἐν δ' ὄρος αὐτῇ
Νήριτον εἰνοσίφυλλον, ἀριπρεπέες: ἀμφὶ δὲ νῆσοι
πολλαὶ ναιετάουσι μάλα σχεδὸν ἀλλήλησι,

¹ 'rigged' corrected to 'rugged' in Lattimore's translation of *τρηχεῖαν* (J.C./R.McC.).

Δουλίχιόν τε Σάμη τε και ὑλήεσσα Ζάκυνθος.

I dwell in clearly seen Ithaca. In it is a mountain with quivering foliage and conspicuous, Neritos. Around it there lie many islands very close to each other, Doulichion, Samē and wooded Zacynthos.²

There is a mountain called Neritos in Ithaca and many islands are ‘around’ (ἀμφί) Ithaca. The kingdom included Samos, or Samē (Kefalonia), to the west and Zakynthos to the south. Leukas to the north-east is also nearby (though not part of his kingdom) and there are small islands to the east, between Ithaca and the mainland of Acarnania. ‘Around’, ἀμφί, is crucial in the identification of Ithaki with Ithaca (*Hom. Od.* 9.22).

The neighbour of Odysseus in the Catalogue of Ships is Meges. His kingdom consisted at the beginning of the Trojan War of the ‘holy islands Echinai’ and Doulichion (*Hom. Il.* 2.625–630):

οἳ δ' ἐκ Δουλιχίου Ἐχινάων θ' ἱεράων
νήσων, αἱ ναίουσι πέρην ἄλως Ἥλιδος ἄντα,
τῶν αὖθ' ἠγεμόνευε Μέγης ἀτάλαντος Ἄρηϊ
Φυλείδης, ὃν τίκτε Διὶ φίλος ἱππότα Φυλεύς,
ὃς ποτε Δουλίχιον δ' ἀπενάσσατο πατρὶ χολωθείς:
τῷ δ' ἅμα τεσσαράκοντα μέλαινα νῆες ἔποντο.

They who came from Doulichion and the sacred Echinai, islands, where men live across the water from Elis, Meges was the leader of these, a man like Ares, Phyleus' son, whom the rider dear to Zeus had begotten, Phyleus, who angered with his father had settled Doulichion. Following along with him were forty black ships.

The Echinai cannot be other than the isles called also Echinades; they lie close to the mouth of the river Achelous and some of them have been joined to the mainland by silting. The position of Doulichion has been much debated from ancient times onwards. The only serious claimant is Leukas, which at various times has been connected to Acarnania or separated from

² Huxley's translation.

it by a canal. Homer does not call Leukas by that name — he refers only to the Leukadian rock, the white cliffs of the south-western promontory of Leukas (Hom. *Od.* 24.11):

παρ δ' ἴσαν Ὠκεανοῦ τε ῥοὰς καὶ Λευκάδα πέτρην,

They went along, and passed the Ocean stream, and the Leukadian
rock³

And Doulichion was according to the poet rich in wheat (Hom. *Od.* 14.335):

ἀνδρῶν Θεσπρωτῶν ἐς Δουλίχιον πολύπυρον.

... a ship of Thesprotian / men happened then to be sailing for
Doullichion, rich in wheatfields ...

And it sent the largest number of suitors to woo Penelope, 52 (Hom. *Od.* 16.247):

ἐκ μὲν Δουλιχίουο δύο καὶ πεντήκοντα

... From Dulichion there are two and fifty

From this we can conclude that the island was large.

Leukas, formerly Doulichion in the kingdom of Meges, fits well into the political geography of the Catalogue of Ships. Meges ruled over the small islands of the Echinades, but also over the large and rich island of Doulichion–Leukas, to the north of Odysseus in Ithaca.

The question now arises: if Meges ruled over Doulichion–Leukas, where were the mainland possessions of Odysseus? To that question Homer provides an answer. When, following the slaughter of Penelope's suitors, Odysseus at last meets his father, Laertes, the old man wishes that he had still been strong enough to join in the attack on the suitors; as strong as, when commanding the Kefallenians, he had taken the stronghold of Nerikos on the mainland cape, see Hom. *Od.* 24.375–381:

τὸν δ' αὖ Λαέρτης πεπνυμένος ἀντίον ἤυδα:
'αἶ γάρ, Ζεῦ τε πάτερ καὶ Ἀθηναίη καὶ Ἄπολλον,
οἷος Νήρικον εἶλον, ἐϋκτίμενον πτολίεθρον,

³ 'Leukadian rock' substituted for Lattimore's translation 'White Rock' here (K.N.).

ἀκτὴν ἠπειρίοιο, Κεφαλλήνεσσιν ἀνάσσω,
τοῖος ἐὼν τοι χθιζὸς ἐν ἡμετέροισι δόμοισιν,
τεύχε' ἔχων ὤμοισιν, ἐφεστάμεναι καὶ ἀμύνειν
ἄνδρας μνηστήρας ...'

Then in turn the thoughtful Laertes said to him in answer:
'O father Zeus, Athene and Apollo, if only as I was when, lord of
the
Kephalenians, I took
Nerikos, the strong-founded citadel on the mainland
cape; if only I could have been such yesterday in the palace,
with armor upon my shoulders, to stand beside you and fight off
the suitors' attack ...'

The cape at the north-western extremity of Acarnania is Aktion, and Cape Aktion can hardly be other than the Aktē of the mainland to which Laertes refers. (See the *Periplous* of Pseudo-Skylax who, in the mid-fourth century BC, described the circumnavigation of the coasts of the Mediterranean and the Black Sea: ps.-Skyl. 1.36):

And outside the Ambrakic gulf are the following <cities>:
Anaktorion with a harbour; Akte; and the city of Leukas with a
harbour: this city stands forth upon the Leukatas, which is a
promontory <visible> from afar <in> the sea. This city was
previously also named Epileukadioi. And the Akarnanes, having
fought a civil war, took out of Corinth one thousand new settlers;
and the new settlers, having killed these people, hold their territory
themselves. And this territory is now an island, having been cut off
at the isthmus with a ditch. And after these places is the city of
Phara; and by these places there is the island of Ithake, with a city
and a harbour. After these places the island of Kephalenia.⁴

Hereabouts lay Nerikos, a citadel (not to be confused with Neritos the mountain and district of Ithaca). The north-western extremity of Acarnania was specifically called Aktē. According to Strabo, the

⁴ Huxley's text cites ps.-Skyl. 1.36, but the quote supplied here corresponds to 1.34 in Shipley's 2011 edition of the text and translation (K.N.).

Corinthians transferred Nerikos to the vicinity of their channel separating Leukas from the mainland (see Str. 10.2.8):

In early times Leukas was a peninsula of Acarnania, but the poet calls it ‘shore of the mainland,’ using the term ‘mainland’ for the country which is situated across from Ithaca and Cephallenia; and this country is Acarnania. And therefore, when he says, ‘shore of the mainland,’ one should take it to mean ‘shore of Acarnania.’ And to Leukas also belonged, not only Nericus, which Laertes says he took ‘verily I took Nericus, well-built citadel, shore of the mainland, when I was lord over the Cephallenians’ but also the cities which Homer names in the *Catalogue* ‘and dwell in Crocyleia and rugged Aegilips’.

Hereabouts it is also placed by Thucydides (Thuc. 3.7.4–5):

The inhabitants, however, showing no signs of submitting, he dismissed the land forces and himself sailed to Leukas, and making a descent upon Nerikos was cut off during his retreat, and most of his troops with him, by the people in those parts aided by some coastguards.

But the Nerikos taken by Laertes was closer to Cape Aktion, farther to the north. Thus, the mainland territory of Odysseus extended along the Aktē, to the north of Doulichion–Leukas, which was the principal part of the island realm of Meges.

As for the lands opposite the mainland in the Catalogue of Ships, the ἀντιπέραια, they may hypothetically be placed facing the mainland or ἤπειρος somewhere in the neighbourhood of modern Preveza on the northern shore of the Ambracian Gulf. (See Hom. *Il.* 2.635):

οἳ τ’ ἤπειρον ἔχον ἢ δ’ ἀντιπέραι’ ἐνέμοντο

those who held the mainland and the places next to the crossing

It follows that the kingdom of Laertes, and later of Odysseus, reached from the coast of the mainland to the north of Doulichion–Leukas as far south as Zakynthos, together with possible rights to grazing land in Elis, such as were exercised by Noemon. He was the son of Phronios, a man of Ithaca who kept his mares and mules in Elis on the Peloponnesian mainland. Speaking about Telemachus, Noemon said (Hom. *Od.* 4.634–637):

νήά μοι οἴχετ' ἄγων· ἐμέ δὲ χρεὼ γίγνεται αὐτῆς
Ἕλιδ' ἐς εὐρύχορον διαβήμεναι, ἔνθα μοι ἵπποι
δώδεκα θήλειαι, ὑπὸ δ' ἡμίονοι ταλαεργοὶ
ἀδμήτες· τῶν κέν τιν' ἔλασσάμενος δαμασαίμην.

He has gone, and taken my ship, and now I find that I need her
for crossing over to spacious Elis, where I have a dozen
horses, mares, and suckling from them hard-working unbroken
mules; I would like to break one in, taking it from the others.

On the west their kingdom also included Samos–Samē (Kefalonia) and the inhabitants of the entire realm were called Kephallenes.

The recognition of the full extent of Odysseus' realm from north to south brings us to one of the most contentious and most ancient problems of Homeric geography. As we have seen in Hom. *Od.* 9.21–28, Odysseus, having identified himself to Alkinoos, tells the Phaeacian king that there are many islands around (ἄμφι) Ithaca i.e. Doulichion (that is, later, Leukas), Samē (that is, later, Kefalonia) and wooded Zakynthos.

21 ναιετάω δ' Ἰθάκην εὐδείελον· ἐν δ' ὄρος αὐτῆ
22 Νήριτον εἰνοσίφυλλον, ἀριπρεπές· ἀμφι δὲ νῆσοι
23 πολλαὶ ναιετάουσι μάλα σχεδὸν ἀλλήλησι,
24 Δουλίχιόν τε Σάμη τε καὶ ὕληεσσα Ζάκυνθος.

I dwell in clearly seen Ithaca. In it is a mountain with quivering foliage and conspicuous, Neritos. Around it there lie many islands very close to each other, Doulichion, Samē, and wooded Zakynthos.⁵

Homer now goes on to say:

25 αὐτῆ δὲ χθαμαλῆ πανυπερτάτη εἰν ἀλί κεῖται
26 πρὸς ζόφον, αἱ δὲ τ' ἄνευθε πρὸς ἥω τ' ἠελίον τε,

It, however, is low-lying and entirely uttermost in the sea towards the gloom but the others are apart toward the dawn and the sun.⁶

But αὐτῆ (she or it in line 25) is 'low' (χθαμαλή) and lies in the sea 'altogether highest up' or 'farthest' (πανυπερτάτη) 'towards the gloom'

⁵ Huxley's translation.

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(πρὸς ζόφον), but the ‘others’ (other isles) are ‘apart towards the dawn and the sun’ (πρὸς ἡῶ τ’ ἡέλιόν τε).

αὐτή here is generally supposed to refer to Ithaca, but there are difficulties in the identification:

1. Ithaca is not ‘low’: it has the mountains of Neritos and Neion on it. The poet says ‘low’, not ‘lower’, so nor is it proper to claim that ‘lower than the mountains of Kefalonia’ is the meaning.
2. Odysseus has just stated that there are many islands around Ithaca and near to each other. He cannot then go on to say that Ithaca is entirely farthest away from them — the force of the superlative, prefixed by παν- ‘altogether’, is strong and deliberate.
3. ‘The others’ are ‘apart towards the dawn and the sun’, and not ‘towards the gloom’ (πρὸς ζόφον). The last expression is sometimes supposed to mean ‘towards the sunset’, and so ‘towards the west’, but at sunset there is still light, as indeed there already is at dawn and sunrise. ‘Towards the dawn and the sun’ is best interpreted as a composite notion signifying all the directions from which light comes, according to season and time of day. The directions are from north of east to north of west. What is left is northwards, that is ‘towards the gloom’, whence comes no daylight. Strabo’s discussion of ‘towards the gloom’ is convoluted, but he has the merit of recognising that the expression ‘towards the gloom’ means northwards (Str. 10.2.12):

ἀλλὰ πανυπερτάτην πρὸς ζόφον, οἷον ὑπὲρ πάσας ἐσχάτην τετραμμένην
πρὸς ἄρκτον: τοῦτο γὰρ βούλεται λέγειν τὸ πρὸς ζόφον, τὸ δ’ ἐναντίον
πρὸς νότον

but the farthest advance towards darkness, (πρὸς ζόφον) that is, placed towards the north more than all the other islands, for this is what the poet means by ‘towards darkness’, the contrary to which is towards the south (πρὸς νότον).

For all these reasons it is clear that αὐτή (she or it) cannot indicate Ithaca. The word is corrupted and in need of emendation. Αἴθη should be corrected to ΑΚΤΗ. Homer is referring, through Odysseus, to the Aktē, the most northerly parts of his realm. The Aktē is low-lying beside Cape Aktion. It is farthest to the north among the domains of Odysseus which,

as we learn from the Catalogue of Ships, included possessions on the mainland. Laertes consistently states that Nerikos, conquered by the Kefallenians under his leadership, was the cape of the mainland with sea on both sides.

Odysseus goes on to say that he cannot regard any land as a sweeter thing than his own. Ithaca is rough but a good nursing mother (Hom. *Od.* 9.27):

ἀλλ' ἀγαθή κουροτρόφος: οὐ τοι ἐγώ γε
ἤς γαίης δύναιμι γλυκερώτερον ἄλλο ἰδέσθαι.

a rugged isle, but a good nurse of young men; and for myself no
other thing can I see sweeter than one's own land.

The pattern of the geographical narrative is thus: Ithaca and its neighbours; next, for the sake of completeness, the northerly part of the realm; finally, the character of Ithaca itself. The corruption of ἀκτή to αὐτή is easily explained. Early Attic and central Ionic Κ was changed to Υ (upsilon) under the influence of αὐτή (Ithaca) just before (Hom. *Od.* 9.21) and of αὐτή δὲ χθαμαλή κείται in the description by Odysseus of Circe's isle (Hom. *Od.* 10.196).

The compelling arguments for identifying modern Ithaki with Homeric Ithaca (see Map 2, page 29) are strengthened, if strengthening is needed, by details of topography in the *Odyssey*. Let us begin with the position of the islet Asteris, 'the starry one'. Homer states that there is an island in the midst of the sea 'between Ithaca and rugged Samos'. It is called Asteris and is not large. There are double (ἀμφίδυμοι) harbours within it (ἔνι) offering safe anchorage (ναύλοχοι). There the Achaeans, that is the ship-borne suitors, waited to ambush Telemachus on his return voyage from Pylos. (Hom. *Od.* 4.842–847):

μνηστῆρες δ' ἀναβάντες ἐπέπλεον ὑγρά κέλευθα
Τηλεμάχῳ φόνον αἰπὺν ἐνὶ φρεσὶν ὀρμαίνοντες.
ἔστι δὲ τις νῆσος μέσση ἄλι πετρῆεσσα,
μεσσηγὺς Ἰθάκης τε Σάμοιό τε παιπαλοέσσης,
Ἄστερις, οὐ μεγάλη: λιμένες δ' ἔνι ναύλοχοι αὐτῇ
ἀμφίδυμοι: τῇ τόν γε μένον λοχόωντες Ἀχαιοί.

But the suitors went aboard and sailed out into the flowing

ways, in their hearts devising sudden death for Telemachos.
There is a rocky island there in the middle channel
halfway between Ithaca and towering Samos,
called Asteris, not large, but it has a double anchorage
where ships can be hidden. There the Achaians waited in ambush.

The white islet sometimes called Daskalio — the name comes from Italian *scoglio*, rock — lies in the channel between Kefalonia and Ithaca, not far from Polis Bay in Ithaca, but closer to the Kefalonian shore. It is not large enough to furnish two harbours, or even one (as a landing there with the McCabes made clear) but the white limestone strata shine brightly in sunlight. Aptly does Homer call Asteris rocky, *πετρήεσσα* (Hom. *Od.* 4.844). The islet is, however, so small that ἐνι, ‘within it’, cannot entail that the two anchorages are in Asteris, one at each end. Either, then, the twin harbours are ‘within’ Asteris because they are close by on the Kefalonian shore nearby or, since ἀμφί (in ἀμφίδυμοι) can mean ‘on either side’, the suitors and their ships waited on both sides of the islet, sometimes in a bay nearby in Kefalonia, at others in Polis Bay in Ithaca. The ships stayed in harbour by daylight, while the suitors were on lookout down the channel expecting Telemachus and his crew to return that way from Pylos to the south. By day the suitors kept watch in turns on the ‘windy heights’ but they put to sea at night (Hom. *Od.* 16.365–370):

ἤματα μὲν σκοποὶ ἴζον ἐπ’ ἀκριας ἠνεμοέσσας
αἰὲν ἐπασσύτεροι: ἅμα δ’ ἡελίῳ καταδύντι
οὐ ποτ’ ἐπ’ ἠπείρου νύκτ’ ἄσαμεν, ἀλλ’ ἐνὶ πόντῳ
νηϊ̄ θοῆ̄ πλείοντες ἐμίνομεν Ἡῶ̄ δῖαν,
Τηλέμαχον λοχῶντες, ἵνα φθίσωμεν ἐλόντες
αὐτόν ...

In the daytime we sat watchful along the windy headlands,
always succeeding each other, but when the sun set, we never
lay through the night on the dry land, but always on the open
water, cruising in a fast ship, we waited for the divine dawn,
watching to ambush Telemachos, so that we could cut him
off ...

Telemachus, however, on the instructions of Athena, did not return by way of the channel, instead he landed near the hut of Eumaeus at the south of Ithaca.

Local geographical knowledge is also evident in the narrative of the return journey of Telemachus. Athena tells him to sail by night keeping away from the islands (ἐκάς νήσων Hom. *Od.* 15.33), since the suitors are waiting in ambush in the sound between Ithaca and Samos (Kefalonia). He is instead to make for the ‘first cape’, that is the nearest one in Ithaca at the south-eastern extremity of the island (Hom. *Od.* 15.36):

ἀλλὰ ἐκάς νήσων ἀπέχριν εὐεργέα νῆα,
νυκτὶ δ' ὁμῶς πλείειν: πέμψει δέ τοι οὔρον ὄπισθεν
ἀθανάτων ὅς τις σε φυλάσσει τε ρύεται τε.
αὐτὰρ ἐπὴν πρώτην ἀκτὴν Ἰθάκης ἀφίκηαι,
νῆα μὲν ἔς πόλιν ὀτρύναι καὶ πάντας ἐταίρους,
αὐτὸς δὲ πρῶτιστα συβώτην εἰσαφικέσθαι,
ὅς τοι ὑῶν ἐπίουρος, ὁμῶς δέ τοι ἦπια οἶδεν.

But you must keep your well-made ship away from the islands,
and sail with the night, and that one of the immortals who watches
over you and guards you will send a following stern wind.
But when you make land, at the first promontory on Ithaca,
then speed your ship and all your companions along to the city,
but you yourself go first of all to the swineherd, that man
who is in charge of the pigs, and whose thoughts toward you are
kindly.

(Hom. *Od.* 15.33–39)

Obediently, Telemachus and his crew pass the Sharp Islands (see Map 1, page 28) near the mouth of the Achelous River and then make for a landing in Ithaca out of sight and out of reach of the suitors, who are waiting near Asteris. The crew are then ordered to sail northwards to a harbour below the polis of Ithaca. Telemachus swiftly climbs up to the hut of the faithful swineherd Eumaeus, whose dwelling is best placed on the Marathia plateau in the south of the island.

Odysseus has already come in disguise to Eumaeus. Having been put ashore by the Phaeacian mariners, he is shown by the goddess Athena, who helps him to store his treasure in a Cave of the Nymphs, that he is back in

Ithaca at last. (If this Cave of the Nymphs is the cave of Marmarospilio, several hundred feet uphill from Dexia Bay, which is conventionally identified with the Bay of Phorkys in Hom. *Od.* 13.345, then assistance from the goddess in the storage would have been needed). (Hom. *Od.* 13.344–348):

ἀλλ' ἄγε τοι δείξω Ἰθάκης ἔδος, ὄφρα πεποιθήης.
Φόρκυκος μὲν ἔσθ' ἐστὶ λιμῆν, ἀλίαιο γέροντος,
ἧδε δ' ἐπὶ κρατὸς λιμένος τανύφυλλος ἐλαίη:
ἀγχόθι δ' αὐτῆς ἀντρον ἐπήρατον ἠεροειδές,
ἶρόν νυμφάων, αἱ νηϊάδες καλέονται

Come, I will show you settled Ithaca, so you will believe me.
This is the harbor of the Old Man of the Sea, Phorkys,
and here at the head of the harbor is the olive tree with spreading
leaves, and nearby is the cave that is shaded, and pleasant,
and sacred to the nymphs who are called the Nymphs of the
Wellsprings,
Naiads. ...

It is most unlikely that Odysseus would have hidden his treasure close to the polis and to the suitors. The cave would have been farther south and not far from the hut of Eumaeus. The Cave of the Tripods, beside Polis Bay, renowned for its tripods placed there about 800 BC cannot be in the poet's mind, but those tripods would perhaps have suggested to him that the Phaeacian treasure of Odysseus should include tripods. From the Cave of the Nymphs Odysseus made his way, as instructed, over the uplands to Eumaeus. We learn incidentally that Eumaeus and his workers tended the swine near to the Raven's Rock and the Fountain of Arethusa (Hom. *Od.* 13.407–408):

δήεις τόν γε σύεσσι παρήμενον: αἱ δὲ νέμονται
παρ Κόρακος πέτρῃ ἐπὶ τε κρήνῃ Ἀρεθούσῃ

You will find him posted beside his pigs, and these are herded
near the Rock of the Raven and beside the spring Arethousa

Both rock and fountain are suitably identified by the cliff and spring from which the visitor may look down upon the little island of Perapegadia: it lies off the south-eastern shore of Ithaca, north of Cape St. John or Cape Mounda (see Map 2, page 29). That Eumaeus lived far from the Big House

of Odysseus in the south of the island is indicated by the swineherd's taking a whole day to walk from his hut to bear news for Penelope that Telemachus has returned safely from Pylos. The swineherd walks to the polis, does not delay there, and comes back to the hut in the course of one day: the journey was perhaps 30 miles, but not beyond the capacity of a stalwart countryman. Independently, two Ithacans assured me that such a walk, to and fro in one day, dawn to dusk, is possible.

Three other features of Ithacan topography are readily identifiable. First is the Ridge of Hermes. When Eumaeus had given to a herald the message for delivery to Penelope, he set out on his return journey: when he was on the ridge overlooking the polis of Ithaca, he saw a ship full of men armed with shields and swords entering 'our harbour' (Hom. *Od.* 16.465–475):

οὐκ ἔμελέν μοι ταῦτα μεταλλῆσαι καὶ ἐρέσθαι
 ἄστυ καταβλώσκοντα: τάχιστα με θυμὸς ἀνώγει
 ἀγγελίην εἰπόντα πάλιν δεῦρ' ἀπονέεσθαι.
 ὠμήρησε δέ μοι παρ' ἐταίρων ἄγγελος ὠκύς,
 κῆρυξ, ὃς δὴ πρῶτος ἔπος σῆ μητρὶ ἔειπεν.
 ἄλλο δέ τοι τό γε οἶδα: τὸ γὰρ ἴδον ὀφθαλμοῖσιν.
 ἦδη ὑπὲρ πόλιος, ὅθι θ' Ἑρμαιοσ λόφος ἐστίν,
 ἦα κίων, ὅτε νῆα θοὴν ἰδόμην κατιούσαν
 ἐς λιμέν' ἡμέτερον: πολλοὶ δ' ἔσαν ἄνδρες ἐν αὐτῇ,
 βεβρίθει δὲ σάκεσσι καὶ ἔγχεσιν ἀμφιγύοισι:
 καὶ σφέας ὥϊσθην τοὺς ἔμμεναι, οὐδέ τι οἶδα.

It was not on my mind to go down through the city, nor to ask,
 nor try to find out; rather the will was urgent within me
 to speak my message with all speed and be on my way back here.
 But one of your fellows as a swift messenger joined my company,
 the herald; he was the first who told the word to your mother.
 But here is another thing I know; with my eyes I saw it.
 I was above the city, where the Hill of Hermes is, making
 my way along, when I saw a fast vessel coming into
 our harbor, making inshore, and many men were aboard her,
 and she was loaded with shields and leaf-headed spears. Then I
 thought
 that these would be the men we mean, but I do not know it.

The name Polis Bay still recalls that the principal settlement of ancient Ithaca lay thereabouts. The Ridge of Hermes overlooking the polis and its bay can be identified with the ridge extending northwards from the village of Stavros towards Pelikata. A high place on the ridge would be a suitable position for the Big House of Odysseus (see Map 2, page 29). Such a structure has yet to be found, but work by the British School at Athens in the 1930s and by the University of Ioannina some six decades later has shown that there was extensive habitation in Mycenaean times in localities between the bay and the ridge.

From certain points on the ridge, not only Polis Bay can be seen but also Frikes Bay to the east. When Athena, in the guise of Mentès the Taphian chieftain, converses with Telemachus at the entrance to the Big House of Odysseus, she points to her vessel, νηὺς δέ μοι ἦδ', 'this ship of mine' (Hom. *Od.* 1.185) afar off in the harbour of Rheithron (Torrent), away from the polis underneath Mount Neion (Hom. *Od.* 1.185–186):

νηὺς δέ μοι ἦδ' ἔστηκεν ἐπ' ἀγροῦ νόσφι πόλιος,
ἐν λιμένι Ρεῖθρων ὑπὸ Νηίῳ ὑλήεντι.

And my ship stands near by, at the country, away from the city,
at the harbor, Rheithron, underneath wooded Neion

Neion, to be distinguished from Neriton, the loftiest mountain of Ithaca farther south, is not certainly identified, but Neion cannot be far from Frikes Bay (Rheithron). As for Rheithron itself (Torrent), it is noteworthy that a winter stream flows through the village of Frikes. The equation of Rheithron with Frikes Bay is the second connection of Ithacan topography with the Homeric text to be made in the surroundings of the polis.

The likely position of a third feature can be inferred. When Odysseus disguised as a beggar is conducted by Eumaeus northwards, they approach the ἄστυ (the polis of Ithaca) and reach the public fountain built by Ithakos, Neritos and Polyktor: water came down from a rock above and there was an altar up above the fountain (Hom. *Od.* 17.204–210):

ἀλλ' ὅτε δὴ στεῖχοντες ὁδὸν κάτα παιπαλόεσσαν
ἄστεος ἐγγύς ἔσαν καὶ ἐπὶ κρήνην ἀφίκοντο
τυκτὴν καλλίροον, ὅθεν ὑδρεύοντο πολῖται,
τὴν ποίησ' Ἴθακος καὶ Νήριτος ἠδὲ Πολύκτωρ;
ἀμφὶ δ' ἄρ' αἰγείρων ὕδατοτρεφῆων ἦν ἄλσος,

πάντοσε κυκλοτερές, κατὰ δὲ ψυχρὸν ῥέεν ὕδωρ
ὑψόθεν ἐκ πέτρης ...

Now as they went down over the stony road, and were coming
close to the city, and had arrived at the fountain, sweet-running
and made of stone; and there the townspeople went for their water;
Ithakos had made this, and Neritos, and Polyktor;
and around it was a grove of black poplars, trees that grow by
water, all in a circle, and there was cold water pouring
down from the rock above ...

Since the two wayfarers have not yet reached the town, the fountain is best placed to the south of the polis. It cannot therefore be identified with the underground ‘well house’, almost certainly of Mycenaean date, to be seen to the north of Stavros village in the vicinity of the so-called School of Homer. The well house is fed by the Blackwater Spring farther uphill to the west, κρήνη μελάνυδρος (Hom. *Od.* 20.158). This may be the spring to which 20 serving women are sent by Eurykleia to fetch water during a thorough house-cleaning while the suitors are not indoors.

In the orchard country to the north-east of Blackwater, Laertes’ garden-vineyard (ἀλωή) can reasonably be placed; here Odysseus, having at first experimentally adopted the persona of Eperitos, is reunited with his father. The false Eperitos states that his ship lay far from the polis out in the country (Hom. *Od.* 24.306–308):

αὐτὰρ ἐμοί γ’ ὄνομ’ ἐστὶν Ἐπήριτος: ἀλλὰ με δαίμων
πλάγξ’ ἀπὸ Σικανίης δεῦρ’ ἐλθέμεν οὐκ ἐθέλοντα:
νηῦς δέ μοι ἦδ’ ἔστηκεν ἐπ’ ἀγροῦ νόσφι πόλης.

My own name is Eperitos; now the divinity
drove me here on my way against my will, from Sikania.
And my ship stands nearby, off the country, away from the city.

The bay is not further specified and cannot be assumed to be Frikes (Rheithron). Aphales Bay, beside the northern extremity of Ithaca, would suit the context but it is less welcoming than Frikes Bay.

In another false story replete with plausible detail Odysseus in disguise tells Eumaeus how he took ship with Thesprotians who were sailing for Doulichion (that is, the later Leukas). Pheidon, king of the Thesprotians, had ordered the crew to convey him to king Akastos in

Doullichion — who, it may be inferred, was ruling there because Meges did not return home from Troy. However, when the ship put in to Ithaca on the way to Doullichion, the crew stripped and bound him, before leaving him aboard, filthily clothed, while they took an evening meal on the shore. With the help of the gods, Odysseus, freed of his bonds, swam ashore and hid in a leafy thicket. Not able to find him, the crew sailed away, and Odysseus was then free to walk to the hut of Eumaeus. The rags add plausibility to the story told to Eumaeus, whose attention is drawn to them (Hom. *Od.* 14.343). The north coast of Leukas–Doullichion can be directly approached from Thesprotia, but it is not hospitable: the most fertile part of Doullichion, an island called by Homer ‘rich in wheat’ (Hom. *Od.* 14.335), is reached from harbours on the south coast. There is local maritime knowledge in the poet’s description of a journey to the southern shore of Doullichion by way of a landfall in Ithaca, for example in the well sheltered Bay of Vathy in the south of the island.

The agreements between Ithacan topography and Homeric descriptions of Ithaca — and the poet’s explanations of the island’s position with respect to neighbouring islands and to the Acarnanian mainland — do not prove that Homer visited Ithaca: certain, however, it is that the poet knew a great deal about the local geography of Ithaca, modern Ithaki. The agreements leave no reason, and no excuse, for placing the home of Laertes and Odysseus anywhere else: they ruled from Ithaca, not from Kefalonia or any part of it, but Kefalonia was a part of their realm. Nor are they at home in Leukas–Doullichion: that island was ruled by Meges before the Trojan War and, for a time, by Akastos after the war; but after the slaughter of the suitors, many of whom came from Doullichion, the island may well have been incorporated into their kingdom ruled from Ithaca — already, in the time of Laertes, Nerikos and the Aktē had become a part of his realm, to the north of Doullichion. Incorporation of Leukas–Doullichion helps to explain why Roman poets called Ulixes (Odysseus) Dulichius. Odysseus can be known as an Ithacan (Ἰθακήσιος) or a Kephallenian, or even as a Doullichian, but his seat of power, his Big House at or near modern Stavros, was in the island still called Ithaca (Ἰθάκη) today.

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Ancient works cited

Ancient works cited follow the abbreviations of the *Oxford Classical Dictionary*.

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Maps

Map 1: Telemachus' route from Pylos back to Ithaca
(after Stanford and Luce 1974, Illustration 86)

Map 2: Homeric Ithaca
 (after Stanford and Luce 1974, Illustration 68)

Photographs

The photographs are kindly supplied by Robert A. McCabe.

Members of the visiting party are welcomed in Ithaca in May 2007.

From left to right: Katerina Dellaporta (director of the Byzantine Museum in Athens), Dina McCabe, Davina Huxley, George Huxley, Christina Kostiri, Georgos Vasilopoulos and Anne McCabe. Mr Vasilopoulos, then Mayor of Ithaca, welcomed the visiting party.

The yacht Aphrodite moored in Kioni Harbour, Ithaca.

George and Davina Huxley on board the Aphrodite.

Huxley writing the careful diary he kept during the voyage.
These diaries now form part of the George L Huxley Papers at the
American School of Classical Studies at Athens.

Huxley checking the Greek Waters Pilot by Rod Heikell.

George and Davina Huxley looking down over the Korakos Petra (Raven's Rock) cliff above Pera Pigadi Bay in the south of Ithaca.

View from Kathara of the adjacent bays of Vathy to the left and Dexia (Phorkis) Bay to the right. It is traditionally believed that Odysseus arrived at one or other of these bays on his return to Ithaca.

View of Polis Bay from the Stavros to Platrithias road, just below the Ridge of Hermes at Pelikata.

A closer view of Polis Bay. The outline of the collapsed cave, excavated by Sylvia Benton in the 1930s, can be seen in shadow at the centre of this photograph, near the farthest boat at anchor.

Huxley at Agios Athanasios / School of Homer. The covers erected by the archaeologists to protect their excavations can be seen in place in this photograph.

Acknowledgement

My good friend and mentor Professor George L. Huxley was an eminent classicist, philologist and archaeologist. He died on 30 November 2022. Over the years we had many conversations about Ithaca, a Greek island with which I have a long association and in which we shared a special interest. Huxley dedicated this essay to his friend the late professor John V. Luce, who was a specialist on Homer.

In 2007, Huxley attended a lecture at the British Museum in London given by the management consultant Robert Bittlestone, who claimed that Homeric Ithaca was not the same island as modern Ithaca but the Paliki peninsula of Kefalonia. Following this lecture Huxley communicated his disquiet about Bittlestone's theories to the well-known photographer Robert McCabe, a trustee of the American School of Classical Studies at Athens while Huxley was director of the Gennadius Library. In response McCabe hired a boat and, that same year, a small party set out for Ithaca and Kefalonia to check Bittlestone's widely publicised hypothesis. Following this trip, Huxley gave lectures at the Universities of London, Harvard and Queens University Belfast. Some ten years later, armed with his lecture notes, I made extensive studies at the British Library and also checked his conclusions on the ground in Ithaca. His words fitted perfectly with the topography of the island and I recorded my findings in my books *Odysseus' Island* and *Walking in the Footsteps of Odysseus*.

This essay was given to Robert McCabe in 2012, but never published. I would like to thank him for his enormous help and generosity in supplying both this essay and these photographs of their 2007 trip to Ithaca and Kefalonia. Many thanks also to the Huxley family for copyright permission to reproduce this work. A big thank-you to Nigel Summerley for checking the text and to Tabby Bourdier for her help with the maps.

To ease the understanding of this essay I have added the quotations in Ancient Greek to which Huxley refers, along with a translation into English. For help with this I owe a big debt of gratitude to Jim Ottaway Jr., a former trustee of the American School, and to Kyriaco Nikias, the editor of this *Bulletin*. Nikias has provided encouragement and advice throughout this project and I am delighted by his offer to publish this essay in the second *Bulletin of the Ithacan Historical Society*.

Since Huxley is not here to cast his eagle eye over this text before publication, I have made absolute minimum edits to his text to improve clarity.

Jane Cochrane, November 2024